

Seriation and Joint Probability: Unifying Archaeological Dates in the Central Mediterranean, ca. 4th-1st c. BCE

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Abstract

Probability theory has been applied to archaeological chronology since the advent of radiocarbon dating, but key chronological indicators, such as artifact typologies, continue to be dated in descriptive terms (e.g., “in the later 3rd c. BCE”). Moreover, the informational inter-dependency for how contexts and assemblages affect others’ dating can become opaque. This paper illustrates the use of two new R packages, *lakhesis* and *eratosthenes*, to construct a wholly formal method for archaeological dating, focusing on the central Mediterranean in the last four centuries BCE. Contextual seriation is used to compare and sequence disparate contexts alongside stratigraphic relationships, to define a joint probability density function. A case study of tombs, stratigraphic units, shipwrecks, and other depositional events is then implemented for the last four centuries BCE, illustrating how the formal estimation of events is achieved. The resulting marginal densities can then be checked against conventional dates, not just to revise typological distinctions and revisit comparisons where discrepancies emerge, but above all to obtain a precise, probabilistic estimation of the occurrence of all archaeological events.

Keywords: dating, chronology, order statistics, beta, uniform, contextual seriation, correspondence analysis, Gibbs sampler, radiocarbon dating, shipwrecks, coinage

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2 Combining sources of chronological information in a formal (i.e., mathematical) way has been
3 a clear objective in archaeology (Levy, 2025; Noukpoape et al., 2025). The development of prob-
4 abilistic methods in chronology has largely centered on radiocarbon dates, dendrochronology,
5 and other scientific methods, in combination with stratigraphic relationships or other historical
6 markers (Aitken, 1990; Bronk Ramsey, 1995, 2009; Buck et al., 1996; Buck and Juárez, 2025;
7 Buck et al., 1991; Dee et al., 2013; Nicholls and Jones, 2002; Steier and Rom, 2000; Taylor
8 and Bar-Yosef, 2014). In contrast, artifact dates—at least in the Mediterranean—have remained
9 largely within the domain of more qualitative or ambiguous periodizations. Artifacts though are
10 key sources of chronological information, whether intrinsically (such as a datable coin) or extrin-
11 sically (in comparison with other finds), and, as this paper shows, their chronological information
12 can be directly into the formal estimation of events incorporated via seriation. The main virtue
13 of this approach is that it allows for the determination of dates in a consistent fashion, using se-
14 riations that are based directly on associations in material culture and measurable by optimality
15 criteria. Representing all events as a probability density function (p.d.f.) not only allows for exped-
16 ient revision of dates, unifying and synchronizing the relationships between events, but further
17 enables the use of more advanced statistical models that can resample from such densities.

18 To those ends, this paper introduces two new R packages (R Core Team, 2024). The first pack-
19 age, `lakhesis`, offers a visual, interactive interface in which to perform seriations (Hahsler et al.,
20 2008; Ihm, 2005; O'Brien and Lyman, 1999), using correspondence analysis (CA) and Procrustes-
21 fit CA (Collins-Elliott, 2026). Here, contextual seriation (i.e., seriation using a binary matrix of the
22 presence/absence of a find-type in a context) is preferred over frequency seriation, since fre-
23 quency or count data is not available for every context, and may not be comparable within the
24 same data matrix (i.e., if one project has reported minimum number of individuals for ceramics,
25 and another sherds); or, there may no quantitative information given at all. Contextual seriation in
26 other words provides a versatile “lowest common denominator” in terms of methodology across
27 datasets.

28 The second R package, `eratosthenes` (Collins-Elliott, 2025, n.d.), provides tools for the esti-
29 mation of the dates of all archaeological events via the input of sequences, finds, and absolute
30 constraints, as marginal p.d.f. This package does not provide functionality for the calibration of
31 radiocarbon dates, given preexisting software (in this paper, `Bchron` by Haslett and Parnell (2008)
32 is used). Rather, calibrated dates are used as input alongside any other absolute markers, which
33 are classified as either *termini post quos* (*t.p.q.*) or *ante quos* (*t.a.q.*). Functions in `eratosthenes` of-
34 fer the ability to check for agreement in the ordering of multiple sequences, constraining them to
35 fixed sequences (i.e., a case one want to maintain an optimal sequence of contexts obtained via
36 seriation given some contexts are known to be in a given order). The date of depositional events
37 are estimated using a two-step version of the Gibbs sampler, and the dates of artifact-type pro-
38 duction, use, and deposition are estimated according to a given rule. The package furthermore
39 allows for the evaluation of the chronological “structure” in place, to determine which contexts
40 are pivotal or influential in determining the dates of others.

41 This paper proceeds to articulate the general approach in the formal estimation of dates,
42 including the use of contextual seriation as a tool for constructing orderings of unrelated de-
43 posits. Seriation, while a mathematical method, is a highly complicated task. No one method will
44 produce the “best” seriation. Hence, optimality measures of the quality of a seriated matrix are

Figure 1 – Locations of all sites which provided relative or absolute dating information for this paper.

45 essential. Nor will every dataset produce a well-seriated sequence. Here, the *detection* of seri-
 46 ated sequences is advocated, which will elicit the familiar curve or arch (the “Guttman effect”:
 47 see Fig. 3) in the CA plot.

48 Following an outline of the general approach taken in this paper, the theory and method
 49 is method is introduced. While probabilistic methods are hardly new, this paper seeks to em-
 50 phasize the construction of the joint density function which expresses the relationship between
 51 events and marginalization of events from that joint density. Seriation affords the means to work
 52 sequences established via comparison directly into that joint density. Finally, a case study is un-
 53 dertaken for the date of depositional contexts, combining depositional events focusing on the
 54 central Mediterranean in the last four centuries BCE, with three core seriations to unify the re-
 55 lationships of various events: funerary assemblages from the necropolis at Aleria; stratigraphic
 56 units from the excavation of Quartier 30-35 at Lattes; and selected shipwreck and other terres-
 57 trial deposits focusing on black gloss ceramics and amphora types (Fig 1).

58 General Approach

59 To start, the philosophy behind the development of this particular approach lay in the spirit of
 60 generalism and minimalism: the goal is simply to estimate the point in time of some event, given
 61 other events that impact or constrain it. Events will either come before or after one another, and
 62 so all samples are drawn along the continuum. No period- or phase-labels are used; only the
 63 instance of the event and its associated materials, in order to compare events with one another
 64 in sequence. In brief, the process entails:

- 65 (1) defining a joint conditional probability density function which expresses the potential
 66 dates of all contexts on the basis of those sequences, absolute constraints, and their
 67 relationships;
- 68 (2) constructing valid sequences of single and stratified contexts and stipulating *t.p./a.q.*;
- 69 (3) sampling from that joint conditional density to estimate dates of any one depositional
 70 event as a marginal probability density function;
- 71 (4) deriving production dates of artifact types, per a stated rule about their earliest appear-
 72 ance;

73 (5) sampling any other dates, such as those of use of an artifact, between dates of production
74 and deposition.

75 This paper focuses on Steps 1-3. The next section discusses the form of the joint conditional
76 density. Marginalizing the date of any one event is accomplished using a two-step Gibbs sampling
77 routine. Gibbs sampling has been conventional in such problems for now several decades, on
78 which see Buck et al. (1996), and the aforementioned sources on radiocarbon dating. Following
79 the discussion of the joint conditional, the logic of seriation is discussed as a way to bring multiple,
80 unrelated contexts into chronological order.

81 Defining a Joint Conditional Density

82 The use of probability density functions in archaeological dating has been well established
83 for a number of cases (see e.g. Bronk Ramsey, 2015; Buck et al., 1996). While probability theory
84 has been applied to select aspects of chronological modeling (e.g., how the p.d.f. of radiocarbon
85 dates changes in light of their stratigraphic sequencing), bringing all sources of dating informa-
86 tion into a single joint density function nevertheless requires some comment (the phrase “joint
87 conditional” is sometimes used as essentially synonymous with “joint,” as the joint entails the
88 product of multiple conditional probabilities). To start, an event is taken as a variate, X_i , within a
89 joint conditional density $f_{X_1, \dots, X_n}(x_1, \dots, x_n)$. The marginal p.d.f. of any one event, $f_{X_i}(x_i)$ conveys
90 the probability of the occurrence of X_i in isolation from the other variates, that is to say, regard-
91 less of their outcomes. To obtain the p.d.f. of just one event’s date, one has to marginalize out
92 the other variates. This marginal p.d.f. of X_i is defined by

$$(1) \quad f_{X_i}(x_i) = \int_{A_n} \cdots \int_{A_1} f_{X_1, \dots, X_n}(x_1, \dots, x_n) dx_1 \cdots dx_{i-1} dx_{i+1} \cdots dx_n.$$

93 To give an initial example, one can consider a single sequence of events in order, between a
94 fixed constant *t.p.q.* ϕ and a fixed constant *t.a.q.* ψ , under the condition $\phi < \psi$:

$$\phi \prec X_1 \prec X_2 \prec \cdots \prec X_n \prec \psi$$

95 where the “ \prec ” symbol indicates “precedes.” The p.d.f. of any one event bounded on the interval
96 $[\phi, \psi]$ is well known from order statistics to comprise a four-parameter Beta distribution, with α
97 is equal to i (e.g., $\alpha = 3$ for the p.d.f. of X_3) and $\beta = n - i + 1$ (Johnson et al. 1995, pp. 214–215,
98 280; David and Nagaraja 2003, pp. 9–13):

$$(2) \quad f_{X_i}(x_i; \alpha, \beta, \phi, \psi) = \frac{(x_i - \phi)^{\alpha-1} (\psi - x_i)^{\beta-1}}{(\psi - \phi)^{\alpha+\beta-1} B(\alpha, \beta)}$$

99 where $B(\alpha, \beta)$ is the Beta function. It can be highlighted that the Beta distribution represents a
100 generalization of the continuous uniform distribution. That is, on the unit interval $[0, 1]$, $\text{Beta}(1, 1)$
101 is identical to $\text{Unif}(0, 1)$. It is clear that if there is just one event between ϕ and ψ , such that
102 $\alpha = \beta = 1$, the p.d.f. in Eq. 2 will reduce to the uniform p.d.f., $f_X(x; 1, 1, \phi, \psi) = 1/(\psi - \phi)$. For
103 discussion of the Beta distribution in archaeological applications, which has not received wide
104 attention, see Baxter and Cool (2016).

105 Beyond a single sequence of order statistics, the marginal p.d.f. becomes more involved, and
106 the definition of the relationships of the events requires more specificity. Take the case where
107 there is just one event X bounded between a uniform variate Φ (as a *t.p.q.*) and another uni-
108 form variate Ψ (as a *t.a.q.*), with $\Phi \sim \text{Unif}(r, s)$ and $\Psi \sim \text{Unif}(u, v)$, where r, s, u, v are fixed
109 constants (i.e., Φ, X, Ψ are not necessarily order statistics between the same two constants). A

Figure 2 – Estimation obtained by simulation of the marginal p.d.f. of $f_X(x)$ with $r = 0, s = 0.2, u = 0.25, v = 1$, given the cases where the absolute constraints Φ, Ψ are either independent of X (Eq. 3) or dependent upon X (Eq. 4) as bounding variates. The black line plots the solution of $f_X(x)$ for Eq. 3, and the brown for Eq. 4, obtained via analysis: see Appendix A.2, A.3, Situation (1), for more details.

110 straightforward solution for $f_X(x)$ depends not only on ordering of the constants, but also on
 111 the independence of Φ and Ψ . Hence, the concept of what “bounded” means above needs to
 112 articulated in terms of the dependence of the variates. Given $r < s < u < v$, the case where the
 113 constraints Φ, Ψ are independent of X , the distributions

$$(3) \quad X \sim \text{Unif}(\Phi, \Psi), \quad \Phi \sim \text{Unif}(r, s), \quad \Psi \sim \text{Unif}(u, v),$$

114 mean that event X has no impact on the estimation of the events Φ and Ψ , while the case where
 115 Φ must come before X and Ψ must come after X can be expressed as

$$(4) \quad X \sim \text{Unif}(\Phi, \Psi), \quad \Phi \sim \text{Unif}(r, \min(s, X)), \quad \Psi \sim \text{Unif}(\max(u, X), v),$$

116 which means that X will affect the estimation of Φ and Ψ , and hence result in a different marginal
 117 density of $f_X(x)$.

118 The change in density can be illustrated via simulation. Figure 2 shows histograms of sam-
 119 ples drawn according to Eq. 3 in comparison with those from Eq. 4. As an analytical solution
 120 to marginalize the p.d.f. $f_X(x)$ requires somewhat tedious calculations, details are given in Ap-
 121 pendix A. Direct computation of the marginal p.d.f. poses challenges in certain cases. E.g., if
 122 one has a case where $r < u < s < v$, one will need to add the requirement that $\Phi < \Psi$ in
 123 order to prevent an impossible situation of an event's *t.p.q.* coming after an event's *t.a.q.* More
 124 discussion on this topic can be found in Appendix A, but, in sum, simulation offers an expedi-
 125 ent means to approximate densities, as otherwise marginalization will involve proceeding case
 126 by case through all possible outcomes and domains of support for howsoever many variates.
 127 Moreover, if one is including constraints whose p.d.f. have been determined via simulation (as

128 is typical with calibrated radiocarbon dates), using simulation to estimate any dependent dates
 129 will be more practical than, say, fitting a model to the simulated marginal p.d.f.

130 Therefore, events across multiple sequences can be expressed with a single, joint density by
 131 indicating which events precede or succede those in another sequences and by bounding their
 132 *termini* at fixed constants or by specified p.d.f. Then, to obtain the p.d.f. of any one date, one
 133 marginalizes out all other variates. The package `eratosthenes` developed to these ends imple-
 134 ments a Gibbs sampler, a mainstay Markov Chain Monte Carlo technique for deriving a marginal
 135 density (Geman and Geman 1984; Smith and Roberts 1993; Buck et al. 1996, pp. 188–193).
 136 Within a Gibbs sampler, one proceeds by sampling variates one by one, holding all others as
 137 fixed. Each variate is updated with a new sample, and then the routine is repeated. The method
 138 of Gibbs sampling developed in `eratosthenes` entails a two-stage process, whereby the sampler
 139 initializes with the earliest possible value for a *t.p.q.* and latest possible value for a *t.a.q.*, perform-
 140 ing an initial, abbreviated sampling routine upon the addition of each variate in order to avoid a
 141 collapse of dates, should a high number of events be inserted into a short interval of time. Then,
 142 the main Gibbs sampling routine is run, to achieve an approximate distribution of the marginal
 143 p.d.f. (more details may be found below and in the package documentation).

144 The “statement” of the joint density, as the inputs of the Gibbs sampler, consist of multiple
 145 sequences of events. For example, letting α and ω represent the earliest and latest possible
 146 events, we can write sequences of events, say, deposits,

$$A \prec B \prec C \prec D \prec E \quad \text{and} \quad B \prec F \prec G \prec H \prec E$$

147 as a set of uniform variates. In cases where we do not have a known ordering for certain deposits,
 148 the relationship is expressed using the operators `min` and `max` to specify whichever is the earliest
 149 or latest:

$$\begin{array}{lll} A \sim \text{Unif}(\alpha, B) & B \sim \text{Unif}(A, \min(C, F)) & C \sim \text{Unif}(B, D) \\ D \sim \text{Unif}(C, E) & E \sim \text{Unif}(\max(D, G), \omega) & F \sim \text{Unif}(B, G) \\ G \sim \text{Unif}(F, E) & H \sim \text{Unif}(G, E) & \end{array}$$

150 On any m th iteration, the Gibbs sampler will proceed by choosing a sample according to each
 151 distribution in the following fashion. Here, all samples are chosen uniformly at random. To draw
 152 a sample $A^{(m)}$, the routine randomly selects a value between α and $B^{(m-1)}$, which is the sample
 153 of B on the previous $(m - 1)$ th iteration. To draw a sample then of $B^{(m)}$, the routine takes a
 154 value from between A^m on the lower bound and then whichever value is the minimum of $C^{(m-1)}$
 155 and $F^{(m-1)}$. Then, for $C^{(m)}$, a random draw is made between $B^{(m)}$ and $D^{(m-1)}$, and so on, until
 156 all variates have been sampled, for a total number of M iterations. As noted above, the use of
 157 the `min` and `max` operators effectively changes the structure of the distribution, “compressing”
 158 or “expanding” distributions of the events as order statistics. Consider that each sequence com-
 159 prises five events, A through E , and B through E . But, stipulating that there are three events
 160 between B and E (F , G , and H) means that there are instead six events between the *termini*,
 161 increasing the parameter of β (Eq. 2) when it comes to estimating any one event. In the same
 162 fashion, the p.d.f. of C and D will be expanded (rescaled) according to the constraints imposed
 163 upon B and E .

164 In defining a joint p.d.f., there is no need to construct a single ordering of all variates. The only
 165 necessity is that there are no discrepancies in the ordering of variates across all sequences, since

166 it is impossible for a variate, i.e., an event, to come both before and after itself. Also, care must be
167 taken that the probability densities of the absolute constraints (which can be of any form) should
168 be appropriately designed for their particular sampling situation. For example, if one has multiple
169 intra-sample radiocarbon dates, which measure the decay since death of the same entity, one
170 has effectively a single posterior density as a *t.p.q.*, which is proportional to the product of all
171 p.d.f. of the intra-sampled dates. If there are multiple radiocarbon dates from distinct entities
172 within, say, a soil deposit (and even other datable *t.p.q.*, such as coinage), then the event of the
173 deposition of that context, X , is subsequent to the latest date of those independent *t.p.q.*, i.e.,
174 $X \sim \text{Unif}(\max(\Phi_1, \dots, \Phi_n), \omega)$, where Φ_1, \dots, Φ_n are the variates of all of the *t.p.q.* Such a case
175 can be found below in the incorporation of radiocarbon dates from multiple, distinct organic
176 elements related to the last voyage of the Mazotos wreck (Manning et al. 2022; see Table 4 on
177 page 15).

178 Marginalizing the p.d.f. of a given date from the joint density is therefore the objective, which
179 depends on providing sequences of events. Developing such sequences may be done via judg-
180 ment on specific cases or positing hypotheses of relationships, or, in the case of archaeological
181 depositional contexts as events, sequences can clearly be obtained from stratigraphic layers (Dye
182 and Buck, 2015). The question arises, then, how to relate multiple sequences, which have no
183 physical relationship to one another. In the following section, the argument is made for a return
184 to seriation (ordination) as a method for sequence construction, relying upon the composition
185 of finds assemblages within contexts, grouping like with like to greatest extent possible. Again,
186 multiple sequences are possible within the joint conditional: the only necessity is that sequences
187 do not conflict with one another in the ordering of their events. Following a description of the
188 method of seriation used in this paper, examples are given of three “core” seriations which com-
189 prise the majority of the scaffolding of the proposed chronology.

190 **The Principle of Best Comparison: Sequencing and Relating Single and Stratified Contexts**

191 While sequences derived from stratigraphy are generally self-evident, creating sequences
192 from unstratified, single contexts requires a stated process. The same goes for multiple, unre-
193 lated, or partial stratigraphic sequences: if one wants to create a single, synthesized ordering of
194 multiple stratified deposits, there needs to be some guiding principle for how they are placed in
195 order. Here, a principle of “proximity by compositional similarity” is invoked: contexts that are
196 most similar in composition to one another (whether in the frequency of types of finds or fea-
197 tures, their presence/absence, or any other comparative rationale) are the most proximate to one
198 another in date. In other words, if the same types of finds occur in two deposits, they are closer
199 in time to one another; if they have different types of finds, the more distant in time they are to
200 one another. This principle is synonymous with the technique of contextual seriation, which is
201 the ordering of contexts on the basis of the presence or absence of a type or feature. Contextual
202 seriation has the benefit of being widely applicable across a broader array of evidence, where
203 quantification of find-types is lacking. As an approach, contextual seriation can be viewed as a
204 baseline, applicable to evidence which has not been quantified.

205 In contextual seriation, a binary matrix is created, with contexts along the rows and types
206 (or more generically, features) along the columns, and in each cell of the matrix, 1 is entered if
207 that type/feature is present in that context and 0 otherwise. Then, the rows and columns are re-
208 ordered to find a most optimal sequence, in which the 1s “move” more or less diagonally as one
209 proceeds down and to the left through the matrix cells (or, up and to the right). There are a variety

210 of techniques available to perform contextual seriation. Here, correspondence analysis (CA) and
211 Procrustes-fit CA were used as they they elicited the most optimal orderings (see Collins-Elliott,
212 2026). In order to judge the quality of resulting seriations, two criteria of optimality are used:
213 Pearson's correlation coefficient squared (where a higher value indicates a better seriation) or
214 weighted row-column concentration (where a lower value indicates a better seriation).

215 It should be noted that not every set of contexts and types *can* be well seriated. Contexts may
216 be perturbed or poorly defined, such that they include material from a variety of periods, just as
217 artifact-types may be chronologically spurious (i.e., they may define aspects of an artifact's mor-
218 phology or function, but those morphological and functional aspects are not sufficiently distinc-
219 tive from those of other artifacts at other time periods). For example, the Lamboglia 3 black-gloss
220 pyxis has been identified both at the finds assemblage of the shipwreck at El Sec near Majorca
221 (Cerdeira, 1987a, p. 243), which conventionally dates to the mid 4th c. BCE, as well as in Tomb 60
222 at Aleria, which conventionally dates to the first half of the 3rd c. BCE (Jehasse and Jehasse,
223 1973, 320 n. 1064). Performing a seriation on materials from the 4th-3rd c. BCE with that type
224 will present a confounded ordering, pulling the ordering of other materials up to a century apart
225 toward one another.

226 Of course, if stratified contexts are included in the seriation, there is the potential for such
227 contexts to be disordered: the depositional sequences of finds cannot be guaranteed to adhere
228 to the most optimal ordering determined by seriation. To make sure all sequences align in terms
229 of their relative order, the function `seq_check()` in the R package `eratosthenes` can be used on
230 all sequences at hand, which will return a `TRUE` value if no orderings conflict. If a `FALSE` value is
231 returned, then the issue can be resolved in two ways. Either, one can simply remove discrepant
232 stratified contexts from the seriated sequence until `seq_check()` passes, or one can use the
233 `seq_adj()` function, which will constrain an ideal, seriated sequence to a fixed, stratigraphic
234 sequence, which is accomplished via piecewise linear interpolation. The `seq_adj()` function is
235 useful for cases of simple misalignments, and this approach can be contrasted with techniques
236 that impose constraints *a priori* to CA (e.g. Poblome and Groenen, 2003; van de Velden et al.,
237 2009). For more extensive conflicts in a seriation with, e.g., a stratigraphic sequence, filtering
238 through the seriation to remove discrepant contexts is the more expedient method.

239 Therefore, one constructs multiple seriations of partial strands (subsets of contexts and find-
240 types), which agree with one another in their ordering. These orderings can be viewed as pro-
241 viding a skeletal or core structure of stratigraphically unrelated contexts, which afford relative
242 constraints for dating all other contexts as much as absolute markers do. Theoretically, it should
243 be possible to construct an entire chronology purely on the basis of relative sequences of events,
244 with only one *t.p.q.* and one *t.a.q.* at the extremes of the sequence, mitigating as much as pos-
245 sible the role played by external events. Such a structure would be tantamount to a chronology
246 based wholly on cultural, social, or environmental features or attributes, without the intervention
247 of political events, such as the destruction of key sites, which are commonly used as absolute
248 markers.

249 Three "Core" Seriations

250 As a way to evaluate the practical issues that arise in developing cross-project seriations and
251 to offer strategies to deal with them, three different situations were explored. First is the case of
252 burials from the necropolis at Aleria, Corsica, which consist of both single and multi-use tombs.

Figure 3 – Top row: the seriated matrices of contexts (rows) and find-types (columns) from Aleria, Lattes (ancient Lattara), and a mixture of shipwreck and other assemblages. Bottom row: plots of the CA/Procrustes-fit CA scores used to produce the seriations.

Table 1 – Statistical information on the core seriated matrices, giving references, dimensions $n \times k$ (number of rows and columns), and optimality criteria: the square of Pearson’s correlation coefficient (sq.cor.) is the square of the criterion developed by McCormick et al. (1969, pp. 147–148); the weighted row-column concentration extends and weights the measure used by Doran (1971). See Collins-Elliott (2026) for more information. The CA plot shows the initial seriation, unconstrained, while the matrix shows the corrected seriation following the removal of disordered contexts.

		$n \times k$	sq.cor.	w.r.c.conc.	
1.	Aleria	Jehasse and Jehasse (1973, 2001)	182 × 2933	0.87	17.17
2.	Lattes (Corrected)	Py (2004)	107 × 217	0.68	6.92
3.	Shipwrecks	See Table 3	24 × 178	0.92	1.87

253 Second, excavations at the site of Lattes in southern France were used to illustrate an approach
 254 with contexts which had sequential constraints by virtue of site stratigraphy. Third, in the interest
 255 of bringing together multiple single and stratified contexts excavated at different times, the case
 256 of shipwreck assemblages along with several other sites were brought together.

257 The contexts in each of these three situations were seriated using `lakhesis`. In the case of
 258 the tombs from Aleria, a more optimal seriation was obtained by Procrustes-fitting the CA scores
 259 (on a symmetric biplot) to the polynomial curve. In the other two cases, projecting scores directly
 260 onto the first principal axis in simple CA obtain more optimal seriations. Figure 3 illustrates the
 261 three seriated matrices on the top row and the appearance of the Guttman effect on the plots of
 262 CA/Procrustes-fit CA scores in the second row. Table 1 shows statistical information on each of
 263 the seriated matrices, namely their optimality criteria, as less optimal seriations should give way
 264 to more optimal orderings (if obtained in the future). Comments about the formation of each of
 265 these seriations follow: it should be emphasized that these seriations are very much provisional,
 266 given the occasional disagreement with conventional dates, warranting future explanation.

267 Contextual Seriation of Tombs at the Aleria Necropolis

268 The necropolis at Aleria, Corsica, excavated and published by Jehasse and Jehasse (1973,
 269 2001), presents a set of 178 tombs, which span the period from the early 5th century down
 270 to the mid-2nd c. BCE. The tombs were initially grouped into three periods (first: 500-350 BCE,
 271 second: 350-250 BCE, third: 250-150 BCE). Here, the catalogue number of finds is prefixed with
 272 Roman numeral "I" to refer to the first volume (Jehasse and Jehasse, 1973), and "II" to refer the
 273 second volume (Jehasse and Jehasse, 2001). There was only one intrinsically datable *terminus*
 274 *post quem* among the finds, n. I 594 from Tomb 41, a Roman *sextans* (rather than a *quadrans*
 275 as reported, since Mercury is on the obverse; RRC 190/5), datable to 169-158 BCE. The other
 276 coinage attested is Carthaginian. As is customary, the catalogue of the material made reference
 277 to comparanda from the necropolis as well as external sources, classifying ceramic forms by
 278 conventional typologies (i.e., for black gloss Lamboglia, 1952; Morel, 1981). In developing a se-
 279 riation, the objective was to maintain, as much as possible, the rough sequence of the tombs
 280 in their original groupings. Since seriation expedites the process of comparison systematically
 281 from what is otherwise lengthy, discursive judgment about the relationship of artifacts to each
 282 another, it was considered that a successful seriation should not completely upend the general
 283 sense of the chronological relationships of finds and types, which is the product of decades of
 284 scholarly labor and consideration.

285 To start, not every tomb from Aleria was included (contexts that comprised redepositional
 286 events of earlier finds were avoided). In the course of plotting the CA scores of the data, extreme
 287 assemblages were suppressed from consideration (what Cool and Baxter (1999) called "peeling
 288 the onion"), to obtain tombs that would elicit a Guttman effect. Not every find-type was included.
 289 Direct, one-to-one comparisons with artifacts from other tombs in fact resulted in the clearest
 290 seriation, while certain general types tended to produce confused orderings. Among these were
 291 Lamboglia forms 11, 21/25, 24, 27, 42A2, 42B, 42A3, 43A, 43A2, and 43B. Progressively sup-
 292 pressing these morphological categories in fact resulted in an ordering where tombs were more
 293 proximate to those in their original phase grouping. Comparisons of metal artifacts and other
 294 small finds also tended to produce poor seriations, given that these associations were often to
 295 tombs in different periods. Keeping the assemblage largely limited to ceramic vessels resulted in
 296 the best elicitation of a (highly angular) Guttman effect. In addition, two shipwrecks were added
 297 as points of comparanda, El Sec and Grand Congloué A, in order to create an overlap with the
 298 third seriation of shipwrecks, as both of these assemblages had some types common to those
 299 from the Aleria necropolis.

300 The most noteworthy shift arose with T. 41. To give some context, Table 2 lists the final
 301 twelve tombs of the seriated sequence at Aleria, also giving the finds from T. 41 which resulted
 302 in its backdated ordering. Dated to around 155 BCE by Jehasse and Jehasse (1973, pp. 231-235),
 303 the intra-site comparisons of its ceramic assemblage in the catalogue largely belonged to tombs
 304 from the later 3rd and earlier 2nd c. BCE, resulting in the tomb being pulled earlier in the seriated
 305 sequence. This had the equivalent result of pushing many of the tombs that were originally dated
 306 to the earlier 2nd c. to a place in the sequence *after* T. 41. Such stated comparisons could not
 307 be justifiably dismissed: Jehasse and Jehasse (1973) compared find n. I 568 from T. 41 with
 308 I 213 (and also with Grand Congloué A, which conventionally dates to the later 3rd or early
 309 2nd c. BCE), Aleria I 569 with I 547, and n. I 583 with I 182, all of which shifted the tomb
 310 earlier in the sequence. All of the tombs that were shifted later, however, were dated generally

Table 2 – The final twelve tombs according to the seriation of the Aleria necropolis, giving the conventional dates according to Jehasse and Jehasse (1973, 2001) and finds belonging to T. 41 that backdated its ordering via comparison with those in other tombs.

Aleria I T. 28	ca. 200 BCE	
Aleria I T. 64	ca. 225-200 BCE	
Aleria I T. 60	ca. 200-150 BCE	
Aleria I T. 41	ca. 155 BCE	I 568 compared with I 213 from T. 24 (ca. 200 BCE), Grand Congloué A (ca. later 3rd/early 2nd c. BCE). I 569 compared with I 547 from T. 37 (ca. end of 3rd c. BCE). I 583 compared with I 182 from T. 20 (ca. 225-220 BCE). I 594 gives a <i>t.p.q.</i> of 169-158 BCE: see Table 4.
Aleria I T. 62	ca. 250-225 BCE	
Aleria I T. 57	ca. 200-150 BCE	
Aleria II T. 149	ca. 250-225 BCE	
Aleria I T. 25	ca. 200 BCE	
Aleria I T. 24	ca. 200 BCE	
Aleria I T. 61	ca. 200-190 BCE	
Aleria II T. 150	ca. 225 BCE	
Aleria II T. 138	ca. 200-180 BCE	

311 to the first half of the 2nd c. BCE. The remaining tombs included T. 24 and 25, dated to around
 312 200 BCE, while T. 61 was placed at the start of the 2nd century; it only had three finds. T. 62,
 313 149, and 150 (originally dated 250-225 BCE) all had six or fewer artifacts, making the number
 314 of comparisons very low with respect to other assemblages and thereby pushing them to the
 315 extreme end of the ordering. Ultimately, though, according the seriation, any tombs after T. 41
 316 should date to the period after 169-158 BCE on the basis of the comparisons in the published
 317 catalogue. Alternatively, the date of the coin as a *t.p.q.* needs to be revisited.

318 Contextual Seriation of Depositional Contexts at Lattes, Quartier 30-35

319 Assemblages from excavations at Lattes (ancient Lattara), Quartier 30-35, were included as
 320 an example of contexts in stratigraphic sequence (Py, 2004). The well-defined systematic typol-
 321 ogy in DICOCER and DICOCER 2 (Py, 1993; Py et al., 2001) was used for the ceramic finds. Just
 322 as with the assemblages from Aleria, contexts whose CA scores were at an extreme distance
 323 on the biplot were suppressed, as were contexts that did not contribute to the emergence of
 324 a Guttman effect. From those contexts that remained, common find-types that were suffuse
 325 throughout the stratigraphic sequence were omitted to discern the most chronologically de-
 326 terminative types. Omitted types included the following: A-AFR TrA; A-ITA Dr1; A-PUN C2a;
 327 CAMP-A 6, 25, 27a-b, 27c, 27Bb, 28ab, 31b, 36; CL-REC 1, 2, 3, 13; CNT-LOR C2, C3, C4, J1a,
 328 J1b, J1c, J4a, V2a, V2b, U7; COM-IT 8e; and DOLIUM bd8f. Such find-types were not removed
 329 entirely from the analysis, but merely temporarily suppressed to obtain an optimal seriation.

330 The resulting contextual seriation, while presenting an “optimal” ordering, did not agree well
 331 with the stratigraphic ordering of contexts. Often, such misalignments were very proximate (i.e.,
 332 a context was placed just before when it should have come just after), but occasionally there
 333 were deposits that occurred far out of phasing. These issues were to be expected: there will be
 334 deposits that are “outliers” in the sense that they contain a few find-types and possibly even
 335 entirely residual material. Surface contexts especially will be prone to contain a chronologically
 336 broad array of materials. While the `seq_adj()` function from `eratosthenes` can adjust simple
 337 cases of such misalignments, the way in which multiple contexts were out of order made it more

Table 3 – Contexts selected for the third seriation, comprising mostly shipwreck assemblages with additional terrestrial contexts which contained transport amphorae and black gloss. See also Cibecchini and Capelli (2013), Loughton (2014), Olcese (2004, 2005), and Vanderersch (1994) for discussion on the Greco-Italic and Dressel 1 family of types, subtypes, and transitional types.

Burriac - Cabrera de Mar (UE 2022)	after 90 BCE	Miró (1991).
Byrsa II B 19 US 4	mid 2nd c. BCE	Lancel et al. (1982, pp. 196–198).
Cap Béar C	ca. 50-25 BCE	Liou and Pomey (1985, pp. 547–551); Parker (1992, pp. 97–98).
Capo Soprano, Gela	–	Benoit (1961, p. 40) connects amphorae from Grand Congloué A to this context, but the precise assemblage remains to be checked as it could post-date the destruction of Gela (Vanderersch, 1994, 73, 209 n. 143).
Cavalière	ca. 100 BCE	Charlin et al. (1978, 48 n. 6); Parker (1992, pp. 133–134).
CIL 15.4537	after 97 BCE	Tchernia (1986, 320 n. 10).
El Sec	ca. 360-340 BCE	Cerda (1987a,b); Parker (1992, pp. 392–394).
Filicudi (Capo Graziano) A	ca. 160-140 BCE	Cavalière (1985); Parker (1992, p. 117).
Filicudi (Capo Graziano) F	ca. 300-250 BCE	Bernabò-Brea et al. (1985); Parker (1992, pp. 118–119).
Gela - Casa Via Polieno	before 282 BCE	Blanck (1978, pp. 96–76); Orlandini (1956).
Grand Congloué A	ca. 210-180 BCE	Benoit (1961) and Long (1987); Parker (1992, pp. 200–201).
Grand Congloué B	ca. 110-80 BCE	Long (1987); Parker (1992, p. 201).
Grand Ribaud D	ca. 10-1 BCE	Parker (1992, pp. 203–204); Hesnard et al. (1988).
Lazaret	late 3rd-early 2nd. c. BCE	Fernández-Miranda et al. (1977, pp. 83–94); Parker (1992, p. 241).
Madrague de Giens	70-50 BCE	Liou and Pomey (1985, pp. 559–567); Parker (1992, pp. 249–250); Tchernia (1978).
Planier C	ca. 60-40 BCE	Liou and Pomey (1985, pp. 553–556); Parker (1992, pp. 316–317).
Punta Scaletta	ca. 140-130 BCE	Lamboglia (1964); Parker (1992, p. 359).
Secca di Capistello	ca. 300-280 BCE	Blanck (1978, pp. 96–76); Frey et al. (1978); Parker (1992, p. 396).
Toulouse, Caserne Niel - Puits 5	mid-late 1st c. BCE	Benquet (2013, pp. 140–142).
Toulouse, Coteaux d'Estarac - Puits 8	1st third of 1st c. BCE	Benquet (2013, pp. 142–144).
Veille-Toulouse - Fosse 40	1st c. BCE	Benquet (2013, p. 146).
Veille-Toulouse - Grande Citerne	2nd half of 1st c. BCE	Benquet (2013, pp. 154–156).
Veille-Toulouse - Puits 4	1st c. BCE	Benquet (2013, pp. 144–145).
Veille-Toulouse - Puits 5	2nd half of 1st c. BCE	Benquet (2013, pp. 152–154).

338 expedient to filter through the contexts, identifying and removing contexts from the seriation
 339 that violated the stratigraphic sequence. The resulting seriation contained 107 contexts from
 340 the set of 667 archaeological events that were entered in from the stratigraphic sequences and
 341 activities, as illustrated in Py (2004, Figs. 17, 37, 74, 97, 204, 230, 243, 267, 295, 317, 346, 382,
 342 and *passim*).

343 Contextual Seriation of Shipwreck Assemblages

344 Finally, a third seriation was produced based on shipwreck assemblages from the following
 345 wrecks, which span the 4th through 1st centuries BCE: El Sec, Filicudi (Capo Graziano) A and
 346 F, Secca di Capistello, Lazaret, Cavalière, Punta Scaletta, Grand Congloué A and B, Madrague de
 347 Giens, Planier C, Cap Béar C, and Grand Ribaud D (Table 3). Additional contexts comprised of

348 amphora types added, such as the silo at Burriac (Cabrera de Mar, Barcelona, UE 2022), which
 349 included a consular date on a Dressel 1B amphora in its assemblage, as well as several deposi-
 350 tions of amphorae from Toulouse (Veille-Toulouse Puits 4 and 5, Fosse 40, and Grand Citerne;
 351 Toulouse Caserne Niel and Coteaux d'Estarac). To illustrate the use of artifacts or contexts that
 352 provided important absolute dating information with only a one or two finds, two contexts were
 353 added: first is the incidence of a Greco-Italic amphora stamp, EYΞENY, from the house excavated
 354 at Via Polieno, Gela (Blanck 1978, pp. 96–76; Orlandini 1956); the second is a Dressel 1B from
 355 Castro Pretorio, Rome, which had a consular date identical to *CIL* 15.4537 (see the explanation
 356 in Tchernia, 1986, 320 n. 10). Also included were amphorae from Capo Soprano, Gela, which
 357 Benoit (1961, p. 40) had compared to those from Grand Congloué A, even though their context
 358 remains to be checked for whether it pre- or post-dates the destruction of Gela in 282 BCE.

359 The sequences of the shipwrecks were already related to those from Aleria by virtue of the
 360 El Sec and the Grand Congloué A wrecks. In order to relate these assemblages to those from
 361 Lattes, the assemblages belonging to Grand Congloué A, Veille-Toulouse - Puits 5, and Carthage
 362 Byrsa II B 19 US 4 were inserted, one at a time, into the dataset from Lattes, Quartier 30-35,
 363 to generate three separate seriations. As three assemblages had much overlap in terms of their
 364 find-types, including them all at once into the data from Lattes would collapse the curve of the
 365 Guttman effect and confuse the optimal seriation already obtained for that site. Hence, adding
 366 them in individually prevented this confusion from happening, such that shorter, partial strands
 367 of seriated sequences which included contexts both from Lattes and those sites were obtained,
 368 which agreed with the optimal seriation and the stratigraphic sequences from those sites.

369 Another short stratigraphic sequence of Byrsa II B 19 US 4 \prec Byrsa II B 19 2 was added
 370 (B 19 2 was not included in the seriation). Additional relationships were added as “hypotheses,”
 371 either relative sequences that agreed with the conventional dating of shipwrecks or absolute con-
 372 straints which were necessary to provide definitive *t.p./a.q.* for the sequences. These hypotheses
 373 are:

- 374 • The deposition of Byrsa II B 19 2, datable to before 146 BCE, occurred between the
 375 shipwrecks at Lazaret (conventionally ca. 160-140 BCE) and Punta Scaletta (conv. ca. 140-
 376 130 BCE).
- 377 • The wreck at El Sec occurred after the wreck at Mazotos, Cyprus, the latter of which has
 378 several radiocarbon dates associated with its final voyage as *t.p.q.* located in the earlier
 379 4th c. BCE.
- 380 • The tombs in the seriation from Aleria are bounded between the dates of 500 and 146 BCE.
- 381 • The deposition of Lattara US 128004 dates to after 225 BCE and the deposition of
 382 US 35236 occurred in the interval of 25-1 BCE.
- 383 • The deposition of amphorae in UE 2022 at Burriac, Cabrera de Mar, occurred before 85
 384 BCE (five years after the consular date on the Dressel 1B amphora).
- 385 • Rirha US 5182 \prec Rirha US 5154 (Callegarin et al., 2016, pp. 40–41). There is no direct
 386 stratigraphic relationship, but Rirha US 5182 is considered to date well before US 5154.
 387 US 5154 in turn is hypothesized to have been deposited before the Planier A shipwreck.
- 388 • The following sequences of shipwrecks hold:
 - 389 – El Sec \prec Filicudi F \prec Tour Fondue \prec Cabrera B \prec Tour d'Agnello \prec Sanguinaires A \prec
 - 390 Lazaret.

Table 4 – *T.p.q.* applied to the contexts in the paper. P.d.f. of the calibrated radiocarbon dates were estimated using the *Bchron* package (Haslett and Parnell, 2008) with the *IntCal20* atmospheric data (Reimer et al., 2020).

Aleria I T. 19	Hypothesis	500 BCE	
Mazotos	VERA-6082a	cal. r.c. p.d.f.	Manning et al. (2022).
Mazotos	VERA-6082b	cal. r.c. p.d.f.	Manning et al. (2022).
Mazotos	VERA-6082c	cal. r.c. p.d.f.	Manning et al. (2022).
Mazotos	VERA-6082d	cal. r.c. p.d.f.	Manning et al. (2022).
Mazotos	OxA-31836	cal. r.c. p.d.f.	Manning et al. (2022).
Mazotos	OxA-31877	cal. r.c. p.d.f.	Manning et al. (2022).
Mazotos	OxA-32005	cal. r.c. p.d.f.	Manning et al. (2022).
Mazotos	OxA-32006	cal. r.c. p.d.f.	Manning et al. (2022).
Mazotos	OxA-32794	cal. r.c. p.d.f.	Manning et al. (2022).
Mazotos	OxA-32795	cal. r.c. p.d.f.	Manning et al. (2022).
Mazotos	OxA-32796	cal. r.c. p.d.f.	Manning et al. (2022).
Rirha US 5182	RH A08 US 5182	cal. r.c. p.d.f.	Callegarin et al. (2016, p. 41).
Lattara US 128004	Hypothesis	225-200 BCE	Py (2004, pp. 71-73).
Filicudi A	Coin - RRC 142/1	189-180 BCE	Cavalier (1985, pp. 107-108).
Aleria T. 41	Coin - RRC 190/5	169-158 BCE	Jehasse and Jehasse (1973, 235 n. 594)
Punta Scaletta	Coin - Ptolemy VI Philometor	180-145 BCE	Lamboglia (1964).
Veille-Toulouse - Fosse 40 sup.	Cos. date on Dr. 1A	103 BCE	Benquet (2013, p. 146).
Dressel 1B - Castro Pretorio	Cos. date identical to CIL 15.4537	97 BCE	Tchernia (1986, 320 n. 10).
Burriac, Cabrera de Mar	Cos. date on Dressel 1B	90 BCE	Miró (1991, p. 57).
Madrague de Giens	Coin - RRC 236	137 BCE	Tchernia (1978, pp. 15-16).
Madrague de Giens	Coin - RRC 382	79 BCE	Tchernia (1978, pp. 15-16).
Madrague de Giens	Coin - RRC 392	75 BCE	Tchernia (1978, pp. 15-16).
Cavalière	Coin - Mazard 50	202-88 BCE	Charlin et al. (1978, 48 n. 6).
Cavalière	Coin - Mazard 45	202-88 BCE	Charlin et al. (1978, 48-49 n. 7).
Cavalière	Coin - Mazard 41	206 BCE	Charlin et al. (1978, 49 n. 10).
Cavalière	Coin - Carteia M SEP / KAR	101 BCE	Charlin et al. (1978, 50-51 n. 11).

Abbreviations: *t.p.q.* = *terminus post quem*; cal. r.c. = calibrated radiocarbon; p.d.f. = probability density function; cos. = consular; RRC = Crawford (1974); Mazard = Mazard (1955).

Table 5 – *T.a.q.* applied to the contexts.

Gela - Casa Via Poliemo	Destruction of Gela	282 BCE	Blanck (1978, pp. 96-76); Vandermersch (1994, p. 166).
Byrsa II B 19.2	Destruction of Carthage	146 BCE	Lancel et al. (1982, p. 194).
Aleria II T. 138	Hypothesis	146 BCE	
Burriac, Cabrera de Mar	Hypothesis	85 BCE	
Lattara US 35236	Hypothesis	25-1 BCE	Py (2004, p. 182).
Grand Ribaud D	Hypothesis (necessary endpoint)	10-1 BCE	Hesnard et al. (1988, p. 145).
Planier A	Hypothesis (necessary endpoint)	1-15 CE	Parker (1992, p. 315); Corsi-Sciallano and Liou (1985, pp. 17-25).

433 to ca. 350-320 BCE, T. 156 to around 300 BCE, and T. 32 to the second quarter of the 3rd c. BCE.
 434 The date of T. 67 largely agrees with its conventional dating, but both T. 32 and T. 156 have been
 435 pushed later. Lattara US 35485, conventionally 150-125 BCE, likewise has been greatly shifted,
 436 this time earlier. The deposition of Byrsa II B 19 US 2, whose material is largely 2nd c., reaches

Figure 4 – Density histograms of the marginal p.d.f. of twelve select depositional events. Results for all 429 sequence events and 33 external constraints can be obtained by running the `gibbs_ad()` function on the data, as shown in the Appendix.

Table 6 – Mean, MCSE, and lower and upper bounds of the 10% highest density region (HDR) of the marginal densities illustrated in Figure 4. Negative dates indicate BCE.

	mean	MCSE	10% HDR (lower)	10% HDR (upper)
El Sec	-354.0	0.59	-358.6	-353.1
Aleria I T. 67	-330.5	0.79	-330.9	-322.3
Aleria II T. 156	-270.2	1.00	-269.4	-261.3
Aleria I T. 32	-216.6	0.67	-221.1	-215.6
Lattara US 35485	-184.2	0.46	-187.3	-182.3
Byrsa II B 19.2	-162.7	0.23	-159.2	-147.0
Punta Scaletta	-143.0	0.19	-149.2	-141.5
Cavalière	-97.1	0.04	-100.9	-99.4
Grand Congloué B	-93.8	0.05	-95.4	-91.8
Toulouse - Coteaux d'Estarac Puits 8	-72.1	0.23	-80.4	-73.9
Madrague de Giens	-56.7	0.33	-65.1	-53.8
Lattara US 35168	-40.2	0.44	-42.4	-37.5

437 its maximum probable date of deposition just before the *t.a.q.* of the destruction of Carthage in
 438 146 BCE. The wreck of Punta Scaletta, which was hypothesized to come after Byrsa II B 19 US 2,
 439 lies within its conventional date range, as do the wrecks of Cavalière, Grand Congloué B, and
 440 Madrague de Giens. Lattara US 35168, which was dated to 100-75 BCE, has been pushed later
 441 by around half a century. The deposition of Puits 8 at Coteaux d'Estarac also agrees with the
 442 conventional date. It should be stressed that these results represent an initial attempt, which
 443 can and will be revised.

444 While it was desirable to maintain conventional dating, shifts in dates are to be expected. At
 445 Aleria, the case of T. 41 was already mentioned. In general, the seriation of the tombs tended
 446 to be placed at equal intervals from 500 to 146 BCE in the absence of additional constraints.
 447 The case of the seriated deposits from Lattes showed larger departures from their conventional
 448 phase dates given by Py (2004), and so more work will be required to comprehend why such
 449 discrepancies have occurred for dates of deposits at Lattes. One consideration is that contextual
 450 seriation may not be ideal for some stratigraphic sequences. After all, in each context, there
 451 might be an amount of residual material which, even if a small quantity, is registered as a “1” just

452 as much as a large quantity of material would be: such a seriation would present more confu-
453 sion than others, such as closed, primary deposits like tombs and shipwrecks (although here too
454 there are cases of mixed and comingled assemblages, it should be stressed). Instead, harmoniz-
455 ing stratigraphic sequences may benefit more from the identification of certain widespread or
456 diffuse find-types, whose earliest appearance at a site constitutes a *t.p.q.* and whose earliest ab-
457 sence serves as a *t.a.q.* Such a method is, more or less, in line with what archaeologists already do
458 in forming chronologies, but here investigators must formally state such hypotheses, which, as
459 a rule, can be applied universally across the entire joint density (i.e., not relying on one find-type
460 for one set of contexts, and another find-type for another).

461 It can be noted also that the single event of the deposition of the Dressel 1B amphora from
462 Castro Pretorio, Rome, had a mean MC date of 43/42 BCE (MCSE 0.36), but the consular date
463 on the amphora was from 97 BCE. The reason for this downdating is that that find consists of
464 a single Dressel 1B amphora, and therefore the contextual seriation placed it in a sequential
465 position that is effectively at the “central tendency” of that artifact type, given all other contexts
466 that contain the Dressel 1B. If this dating is undesirable, the investigator is able to impose their
467 own *t.a.q.* on the event of the deposition of that amphora.

468 Ultimately, the benefit of a unified, formal framework for chronology as proposed here is
469 that one obtains precise, numerical estimates for events, taking into account *all* events for their
470 impact on one another. Any date can be expressed, just as with radiocarbon dates, as a highest
471 density region (HDR), which gives the range of the most probable occurrences of an event. Taking
472 the Madgrague de Giens shipwreck, whose mean estimated date is 57/56 BCE (MSCE 0.33), a
473 narrow range can be taken with a 10% HPD, which covers 65-53 BCE. A broad estimate can
474 be taken with a 95% HPD, which spans the period from 75-15 BCE. Such a date is affected not
475 just by the immediate *t.p.q.* of the coinage on board, but its typological comparisons with all
476 other events in its seriation. A formal approach also has the benefit in allowing one to inspect
477 discrepancies with the conventional chronology, to determine if the causes of disagreements lay
478 in the typological structure of the categories used, the lack of sufficient constraints, or even in
479 the need to insert more hypothetical assumptions. Or, there may be no justifiable excuse for the
480 conventional dating, in which case it should be abandoned.

481

Conclusion

482 This paper has introduced the means and methods to establish chronologies entirely in prob-
483 abilistic terms directly from the act of comparison, via seriation. The quality of a seriation is
484 conveyed via optimality criteria, such that the most optimal ordering can be chosen, and se-
485 quences of contexts can be harmonized with other relative sequences in agreement with fixed,
486 stratigraphic relationships. The continuous uniform distribution offers a default expression of
487 uncertainty for the occurrence of one event between any two others, and absolute constraints
488 are added as variates themselves, resulting in a joint conditional density from which any one
489 date can be marginalized. The main hurdle lies in the question of how to associate unrelated
490 contexts with one another. Here, contextual seriation was advocated as a baseline to measure
491 the similarity of contexts to one another in terms of their finds assemblages; as discussed fre-
492 quency seriation may be more germane for the case of seriated stratigraphic contexts, or any
493 contexts which may include a high number of low counts of residual or sporadic material. Instead
494 of constructing a single “grand seriation,” this paper advocates for developing multiple, partial,

495 “most optimal” seriations, which are constrained to stratigraphic relationships. There is no need
 496 for phasing or periodization in terms of determining the date of an assemblage: events can be
 497 directly placed into sequence via seriation, on the basis of the principle of comparison.

498 The formal chronology developed here that unifies the relationships among depositional
 499 events of the central Mediterranean ca. 4th-1st c. BCE is provisional, needing a fuller review
 500 and the addition of more contexts and typological associations. The relationships established
 501 between artifacts that are formalized via seriation are not novel ones, but the impact of their log-
 502 ical consequences on all other dates can *only* be evaluated against one another in their entirety
 503 via a formal approach. Results from this method are sure to differ from conventional chronology,
 504 since the full balance of how inter-assemblage comparisons and absolute markers affect one
 505 another quantitatively has heretofore not been assessed.

506 Further information and examples are available in the documentation of the R packages
 507 `lakthesis` and `eratosthenes`, which offer more functionality than what can be presented in this
 508 paper (including dating the production, use, and deposition of artifact types). Users are kindly
 509 requested to direct any comments to the author for package improvements.

510 Appendix A. Some Analytical Solutions to Marginal p.d.f. of Dates

511 The following appendix presents some analytical solutions to the marginal p.d.f. of dates in
 512 sequences. As noted above, Monte Carlo techniques are commonly used in the estimation of
 513 p.d.f. where integration is difficult or intractable. Direct computation via analysis is preferable,
 514 though. Where one only has order variates (events in sequences) which are bound by constants,
 515 an analytical solution to the marginal p.d.f. will be tractable, but, depending on the structure
 516 of the joint conditional, it will be of varying levels of difficulty. Strategies include the use of
 517 Fubini’s theorem, as well as polynomial division, integration by partial fractions, and integration
 518 by parts, in order to turn the product of the joint density into a sum of separate terms. Attention
 519 to the domain over which one is integrating is also crucial, with respect to the sequence of the
 520 constraints furnished, in order to avoid impossible outcomes (e.g., a variate which serves as a
 521 *t.p.q.* for others coming before another that is its *t.a.q.*). Incorporating analytical solutions into
 522 the functionality of `eratosthenes` is a current goal.

523 A.1. Multiple Events within Fixed *Termini*

524 The simplest case, of a single sequence of events between two fixed constants ϕ (as a *t.p.q.*)
 525 and ψ (*t.a.q.*) has its marginal p.d.f. given in Eq. 2, where α is the number of the event i and β is
 526 equal to $n + 1 - i$, where n is the total number of events.

527 A.2. Single Event within Variable (Uniform) *Termini*, Independent of the Event

528 The situation of a single event bound between two uniformly random variates presents a
 529 more complicated situation, but an analytical solution exists. Let the *t.p.q.* Φ and the *t.a.q.* Ψ be
 530 uniformly distributed each between two constants, and there is only one variate, X , which is
 531 uniformly distributed between Φ and Ψ . The p.d.f. of X is therefore $f_{X|\Phi,\Psi}(x|\phi, \psi) = 1/(\psi - \phi)$.
 532 Let the *t.p.q.* lie between fixed constants r and s , with $r < s$, and the *t.a.q.* lie between u and v ,
 533 with $u < v$. That is, $\Phi \sim \text{Unif}(r, s)$ and $\Psi \sim \text{Unif}(u, v)$. Given independence in the variates of Φ
 534 and Ψ , one has $f_{\Phi,\Psi}(\phi, \psi) = f_{\Phi}(\phi)f_{\Psi}(\psi)$. That is, the selection of a value for Φ does not affect the
 535 selection of a value for Ψ , and vice versa. The solution to the double integral that marginalizes

536 out ϕ and ψ to obtain $f_X(x)$ is:

$$(5) \quad f_X(x) = \iint_A f_{X|\Phi,\Psi}(x|\phi, \psi) f_\Phi(\phi) f_\Psi(\psi) d\phi d\psi$$

537 In solving for the definite integral, the region of A requires careful attention, since it will change
 538 based upon the ordering of the fixed constants with respect to one another and to the marginal
 539 variate (here just X). While it had initially been defined that $r < s$ and $u < v$, such a definition
 540 results in six different situations to consider for these constants. The first and last of these situ-
 541 ations are straightforward to solve, but the others present difficulties insofar as they result in a
 542 situation where Φ and Ψ are dependent upon one another.

543 (1) $r < s < u < v$. First, the notation $A = [r, s] \times [u, v]$ is abused to represent the domain
 544 $A = \{(\phi, \psi) \in \mathcal{R}^2 : r \leq \phi \leq s, u \leq \psi \leq v\}$. For this domain of A , the solution of the
 545 double integral in Eq. 5 can be made more concise by defining a function,

$$g(r, s, u, v) := \frac{1}{(s-r)(v-u)} \log \left[\frac{(v-r)^{v-r}(u-s)^{u-s}}{(v-s)^{v-s}(u-r)^{u-r}} \right]$$

546 The marginal p.d.f. $f_X(x; r, s, u, v)$ will involve integrating over three different domains of
 547 A . Starting from Eq. 5, the marginal will take the form

$$f_X(x) = \iint_A \frac{1}{\psi - \phi} \frac{1}{s - r} \frac{1}{v - u} d\phi d\psi.$$

548 Applying basic rules of integration for the reciprocal of terms and logarithms, one obtains

$$f_X(x) = \begin{cases} g(r, x, u, v) & \text{for } r \leq x < s; A = [r, x] \times [u, v] \\ g(r, s, u, v) & \text{for } s \leq x < u; A = [r, s] \times [u, v] \\ g(r, s, x, v) & \text{for } u \leq x < v; A = [r, s] \times [x, v] \end{cases}$$

549 This result is illustrated by the black line in Figure 2.

550 (2) $r < u < s < v$, which cannot tolerate a sample where $\psi \leq \phi$ and hence results in
 551 dependence between Φ and Ψ (see Section A.3);

552 (3) $r < u < v \leq s$, which must imply instead a case where $s = v$, and again involves
 553 dependence between Φ and Ψ to ensure that $\psi < \phi$ (see Section A.3);

554 (4) $u \leq r < s < v$, which similarly must imply that $r = u$ and again involves dependence
 555 between Φ and Ψ (see Section A.3);

556 (5) $u \leq r < v \leq s$, which must imply instead a case where $r = u, s = v$ for the same reason.
 557 This is identical to the situation of Example A.1, in which one has three ordered events
 558 (Φ, X, Ψ) bound between two fixed *termini*.

559 (6) $r < s = u < v$. This case will yield the same form of the p.d.f. as Situation (1), only now
 560 as $s = u$, we have:

$$f_X(x) = \begin{cases} g(r, x, u, v) & \text{for } r \leq x < s; A = [r, x] \times [u, v] \\ g(r, u, x, v) & \text{for } u \leq x < v; A = [r, u] \times [x, v]. \end{cases}$$

561 Discussion of these situations where there is dependence among the constraints are
 562 discussed in the following section.

563 A.3. Single Event within Variable (Uniform) *Termini*, Dependent upon the Event

564 Each of the situations in the previous section have counterparts where constraints are de-
 565 pendent upon X , i.e., with $\Phi \sim \text{Unif}(r, \min(s, X))$ and $\Psi \sim \text{Unif}(\max(u, X), v)$, as given in Eq. 4.

566 In Situations (1), (5), and (6), the marginal p.d.f. is straightforward. But for Situations (2-4), I regret
 567 that time has prohibited me from further pursuit of a solution. As can be seen in the Section A.4,
 568 even when analytical solutions are possible thanks to the presence of independent variates, the
 569 computations can be somewhat labor-intensive.

570 (1) This case will result in a trapezoidal density, which has been studied by Lee and Bronk
 571 Ramsey (2012) and van Dorp and Kotz (2003). The marginal p.d.f. of X will be:

$$f_X(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{2(x-r)}{(s-r)(v+u-s-r)} & \text{for } r \leq x < s; \\ \frac{2}{(v+u-s-r)} & \text{for } s \leq x < u; \\ \frac{2(v-x)}{(v-u)(v+u-s-r)} & \text{for } u \leq x < v. \end{cases}$$

572 This result is illustrated by the brown line in Figure 2. Likewise, one can marginalize X , Ψ
 573 to obtain the marginal p.d.f of Φ , and Φ , X to obtain that of Ψ .

574 (2-4) These situations involve the order statistics of dependent variates. As the Beta density
 575 in Eq. 2 has been derived under the assumption that the occurrences of events are inde-
 576 pendent and identically distributed (i.i.d.), the non-i.i.d. case presents more complications
 577 when events are dependent and/or not identically distributed. David and Nagaraja (2003,
 578 pp. 95–112) covers these situations (see also Maurer and Margolin, 1976). One would
 579 need to work through the combinatorics of events with regard to their cumulative distri-
 580 bution function (c.d.f.), and then take their derivative of the c.d.f. to yield a p.d.f.

581 A potential avenue for the marginal of $f_X(x)$ that does not entail working from the
 582 c.d.f. could involve treating separate cases of $[r, u]$, $[u, s]$, and $[s, v]$, just as with Situation
 583 (1). For the case of Situation (4), for example, it would be the case that Ψ is a piecewise
 584 density, not only bound between $[u, s]$ as a Beta density also between $[s, v]$, as a uniform
 585 variate. In order to ensure that the integral of $f_\Psi(\psi)$ sums to one, the p.d.f. $f_\Psi(\psi)$ across
 586 the support of both $[u, s]$ and $[s, v]$ would need to be adjusted by a parameter, γ :

$$\gamma \left[f_\Psi(s)(v-s) + \int_u^s f_\Psi(\psi) d\psi \right] = 1$$

587 which in this particular Situation (4) will be equal to

$$\gamma = \left(1 + \frac{v-s}{(s-u)B(3,1)} \right)^{-1}$$

588 such that for $v = s$, $\gamma = 1$. Then, any decrease in the probability of Ψ within $[u, s]$ will
 589 have an impact both on Φ and X , which will need to be taken into account. Likewise, the
 590 probability of X allocated within $[s, v]$ will have an impact on its distribution within $[u, s]$.

591 (5) This case again presents a situation equivalent to the p.d.f. of Eq. 2.

592 (6) The case of Situation (6) above results in a triangular distribution when the constraints
 593 are dependent upon X , as a reductive case of the trapezoidal distribution in Situation (1).
 594 Where $s = u$, we have

$$f_X(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{2(x-r)}{v-u} \left(\frac{1}{r-v} - \frac{1}{r-u} \right) & \text{for } r \leq x < u; \\ \frac{2(x-r)}{v-u} \left(\frac{1}{r-v} - \frac{1}{r-x} \right) & \text{for } u \leq x \leq v. \end{cases}$$

595 **A.4. Multiple Events within Variable (Beta) *Termini*, Independent of the Events**

596 Marginalizing the order statistics for multiple events in a single sequence, that is, deriving
 597 the marginal p.d.f. of $f_{X_i}(x_i)$ bound between two uniform variates Φ and Ψ , gives way to the
 598 more general problem where Φ and Ψ are themselves four-parameter Beta distributions, given
 599 that the continuous uniform is just a special case of the Beta. Such a generalization means that
 600 one can give the formal equations for any one event, which may be the result of multiple *t.p.q.*
 601 and *t.a.q.* across multiple sequences. Hence, Eq. 1 will integrate the product of multiple Beta
 602 distributions that comprise the joint density. The greater the number of sequences and external
 603 constraints that are included, the more laborious the integral becomes for any one variate.

604 The following example illustrates a simple case of an order variate in one sequence which
 605 depends on another in a second sequence. The first sequence contains three events bound by
 606 two fixed constants, $\phi_1 < X_1 < X_2 < X_3 < \psi_1$. The second sequence is bound by X_2 and
 607 the fixed constant ψ_2 , such that $X_2 < Y_1 < Y_2 < Y_3 < \psi_2$. It is required that $\phi_1 < \psi_1 < \psi_2$
 608 to ensure independence. The marginal p.d.f. of, say, Y_2 can be obtained analytically. Knowing
 609 that X_2 and Y_2 follow a Beta distribution, since they are order variates, $X_2 \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_1, \beta_1)$ and
 610 $Y_2 \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_2, \beta_2)$, with $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = \beta_1 = \beta_2 = 2$ (given that they are both the second out
 611 of three total events). The marginal will therefore be the product of two four-parameter Beta
 612 distributions:

$$\begin{aligned} f_{Y_2}(y_2) &= \int_A f_{Y_2|X_2}(y_2|x_2) f_{X_2}(x_2) dx_2 \\ &= \int_A \frac{(y_2 - x_2)^{\alpha_2-1} (\psi_2 - y_2)^{\beta_2-1}}{(\psi_2 - x_2)^{\alpha_2+\beta_2+1} B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \frac{(x_2 - \phi_1)^{\alpha_1-1} (\psi_1 - x_2)^{\beta_1-1}}{(\psi_1 - \phi_1)^{\alpha_1+\beta_1+1} B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)} dx_2 \end{aligned}$$

613 Just as with Example A.2, the result is a piecewise function, since the domain of A will differ
 614 depending on if $y_2 < \psi_1$ or $\psi_1 \leq y_2$.

615 To start, the information on the parameters is The marginal will therefore be

$$\begin{aligned} f_{Y_2}(y_2) &= \int_A f_{Y_2|X_2}(y_2|x_2) f_{X_2}(x_2) dx_2 \\ &= \int_A \frac{(y_2 - x_2)^{\alpha_2-1} (\psi_2 - y_2)^{\beta_2-1}}{(\psi_2 - x_2)^{\alpha_2+\beta_2+1} B(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \frac{(x_2 - \phi_1)^{\alpha_1-1} (\psi_1 - x_2)^{\beta_1-1}}{(\psi_1 - \phi_1)^{\alpha_1+\beta_1+1} B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)} dx_2 \\ &= \frac{(\psi_2 - y_2)}{(\psi_1 - \phi_1)^3 B(2, 2)^2} \int_A \frac{(y_2 - x_2)(x_2 - \phi_1)(\psi_1 - x_2)}{(\psi_2 - x_2)^3} dx_2. \end{aligned}$$

616 Let $C = (\psi_2 - y_2)/[(\psi_1 - \phi_1)^3 B(2, 2)^2]$. Expanding the polynomial, let

$$a_3 = 1, \quad a_2 = -\phi_1 - \psi_1 - y_2, \quad a_1 = \phi_1\psi_1 + \psi_1y_2 + \phi_1y_2, \quad a_0 = -\phi_1\psi_1y_2$$

617 so that the marginal becomes

$$f_{Y_2}(y_2) = C \int_A \frac{a_3 x_2^3}{(\psi_2 - x_2)^3} + \frac{a_2 x_2^2}{(\psi_2 - x_2)^3} + \frac{a_1 x_2}{(\psi_2 - x_2)^3} + \frac{a_0}{(\psi_2 - x_2)^3} dx_2$$

618 which can be solved per standard rules of integration:

$$\begin{aligned} f_{Y_2}(y_2) &= C \left\{ a_3 \left[\frac{\psi_2^2(6x_2 - 5\psi_2)}{2(\psi_2 - x_2)^2} - 3\psi_2 \log(\psi_2 - x_2) - x_2 \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. + a_2 \left[\frac{2\psi_2}{\psi_2 - x_2} - \frac{\psi_2^2}{2(\psi_2 - x_2)^2} - \log(\psi_2 - x_2) \right] + a_1 \left[\frac{2x_2 - \psi_2}{2(\psi_2 - x_2)^2} \right] + a_0 \left[\frac{1}{2(\psi_2 - x_2)^2} \right] \right\} \Big|_A. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 5 – The marginal p.d.f. of Y_2 according to the situation in Example A.4, with samples in grey. This result occurs for $\phi_1 = 10$, $\psi_1 = 40$, $\psi_2 = 55$.

619 To obtain a more concise representation, let

$$b_1 = 6\psi_2^2 + 4a_2\psi_2 + 2a_1, \quad b_0 = -5\psi_2^3 - 3a_2\psi_2^2 - a_1\psi_2 + a_0$$

620 so that

$$f_{Y_2}(y_2) = C \left[\frac{b_1 x_2 + b_0}{2(\psi_2 - x_2)^2} - (3\psi_2 + a_2) \log(\psi_2 - x_2) - x_2 \right] \Big|_A.$$

621 The region A to integrate over for x_2 will depend on the relationship of y_2 and ψ_1 . If $y_2 < \psi_1$,
 622 then $A = [\phi_1, y_2]$. If $\psi_1 \leq y_2$, then $A = [\phi_1, \psi_1]$. The final form of the marginal p.d.f. will thus be a
 623 piecewise function, for y_2 on the support of $[\phi_1, \psi_2]$:

$$f_{Y_2}(y_2) = \begin{cases} C \left[\frac{b_1 y_2 + b_0}{2(\psi_2 - y_2)^2} - \frac{b_1 \phi_1 + b_0}{2(\psi_2 - \phi_1)^2} - (3\psi_2 + a_2) \log \left(\frac{\psi_2 - \phi_1}{\psi_2 - y_2} \right) - y_2 + \phi_1 \right] & \text{for } y_2 < \psi_1; \\ C \left[\frac{b_1 \psi_1 + b_0}{2(\psi_2 - \psi_1)^2} - \frac{b_1 \phi_1 + b_0}{2(\psi_2 - \phi_1)^2} - (3\psi_2 + a_2) \log \left(\frac{\psi_2 - \phi_1}{\psi_2 - \psi_1} \right) - \psi_1 + \phi_1 \right] & \text{for } \psi_1 \leq y_2. \end{cases}$$

624 Figure 5 illustrates the plot of the marginal p.d.f. of Y_2 obtained analytically along with the results
 625 obtained via simulation.

626 If one were to solve for the other variates, one would change the values of the Beta distri-
 627 bution in the joint density accordingly. E.g., for Y_1 , one would use the values of $\alpha_2 = 1$, $\beta_2 = 3$.
 628 Or, if one were to increase the number of the events bounded by the fixed constants, and/or
 629 change their conditional structure, the number of terms in the joint probability will change, even
 630 as it remains a product of Beta distributions. This of course depends on the use of single-point
 631 constants as the ultimate demarcators of *t.p.q.* and *t.a.q.*; any constraint that is itself a density
 632 that has been estimated by simulation will warrant simulation for marginalizing any dependent
 633 variates.

634

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647 Data, script, code, and supplementary information availability

648 Data and code are available online (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17508911>), in either
649 .rda or .csv and plain-text .r formats:

- 650 • `caa2025_ser20251001.rda` contains the three seriations produced in this paper, which
651 are also downloadable in the following .csv formats as seriated matrices (see Table 1):
 - 652 - `caa2025_ser_aleria.csv` contains the seriated matrix obtained for the tombs at
653 Aleria.
 - 654 - `caa2025_ser_lattara.csv` contains the seriated matrix obtained for stratigraphic
655 contexts at Lattes.
 - 656 - `caa2025_ser_shipwrecks.csv` contains the seriated matrix of the core seriation of
657 shipwrecks and other associated contexts.
- 658 • `caa2025_eda20251001.rda` contains all data regarding stratigraphic sequences and ab-
659 solute constraints. This information was keyed in manually, and the following plain-text
660 .r file contains the text to produce these sequences and constraints.
- 661 • `caa2025_script.r` is a plain text script containing all R code used to produce the re-
662 sults of this paper, including the inputs of the stratigraphic sequences and absolute con-
663 straints.

664 As .rda files are R's interchange format, objects are loaded into memory already named. Se-
665 quences are contained in the `list` object named `contexts_20251001`, `t.p.q.` are contained in
666 `tpq_20251001`, and `t.a.q.` in `taq_20251001`.

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